

Assessment of Alexandria Mineral Oil Company “AMOC” Carbon Footprint

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- **Summary:**

The research conducted on carbon footprint in Alexandria, Egypt highlighted several factors that contribute to carbon emissions, including transportation, energy consumption, waste management, agriculture and land use, population growth, and industrial activity. To mitigate the impact of these factors, potential solutions were identified, including promoting public transportation, increasing energy efficiency, improving waste management, promoting sustainable agriculture and land use, controlling population growth, and promoting clean industrial processes.

Additionally, potential measures to reduce the carbon footprint of Alexandria Mineral Oils Company (AMOC) were suggested, including applying energy conservation principles in all process units, utilizing renewable energy sources, and optimizing water consumption. Prioritization of these measures was also discussed, with a focus on actions that are both effective and feasible to implement.

The implications of reducing carbon footprint in Alexandria and other regions are significant, as it can help mitigate the effects of climate change and improve the health and well-being of communities. The adoption of sustainable practices can also benefit businesses by reducing costs and increasing efficiency, as well as enhancing their reputation and attracting environmentally conscious customers.

This study concluded that the total carbon footprint of AMOC was approximately around 248 ton CO₂e/year during the study period.

Future research in this area can explore the impact of specific interventions and policies on carbon footprint reduction, as well as the economic and social implications of transitioning to a low-carbon economy. Additionally, research can focus on developing new technologies and innovations to further reduce carbon emissions and increase sustainability.

Keyword: Carbon footprint, Greenhouse gas emissions, CO₂ emissions, Emission factors, Energy efficiency, Emission reduction strategies, Energy audits

- **Introduction:**

Definition of carbon footprint

The carbon footprint, defined as the total amount of greenhouse gases emitted into the atmosphere due to human activities, is a critical indicator of environmental impact. This includes activities such as driving, electricity usage, and consumption of goods. Greenhouse gases, primarily carbon

dioxide, contribute to global warming and climate change by trapping heat in the Earth's atmosphere (IEA, 2022). Individual, organizational, and product carbon footprints are measured in terms of carbon dioxide equivalent (CO₂e), considering the global warming potential of other gases like methane and nitrous oxide.

Importance of measuring the carbon footprint

The significance of measuring carbon footprint lies in its ability to raise awareness about the environmental impact of human activities (IPCC, 2022). Understanding one's contribution to global warming is crucial for individuals, organizations, and governments. Measurement facilitates identification of areas for improvement, allowing for the adoption of more sustainable practices. Regular monitoring of carbon footprint aids in tracking progress towards emission reduction goals and enhances accountability (Lin et al., 2022). In some cases, regulatory compliance necessitates the measurement of carbon footprint, emphasizing its critical role in mitigating climate change impacts.

- **Literature Review:**

The literature review explores a comprehensive understanding of the carbon footprint in the context of oil refineries, emphasizing its implications for global warming and climate change. Lin et al. (2022) conducted an in-depth analysis of carbon footprint assessment methodologies specific to oil refineries, shedding light on effective strategies for emissions reduction. Building on this, Sibanda et al. (2021) investigated the influences of process integration on carbon footprint reduction at oil refineries, offering valuable insights into sustainable practices within the industry.

Elgowainy et al. (2021) contributed significantly by focusing on the carbon intensity of petroleum refining operations. This work enhances our understanding of the emissions associated with the petroleum refining process, crucial for devising targeted reduction strategies. The Egyptian Petroleum Sector Emissions Reduction Roadmap (Ministry of Petroleum and Mineral Resources, 2021) serves as a guiding framework, outlining key strategies for reducing emissions in the Egyptian oil sector.

In the broader context of alternative energy sources, Osman et al. (2020) explored the prospects of a hydrogen economy in Egypt and globally, providing insights into potential shifts in energy consumption patterns. Wang et al. (2021) delved into the speciation of carbonaceous compositions within the refinery carbon footprint, contributing valuable information to the understanding of carbon emissions in refining processes.

Vázquez-Rowe et al. (2021) conducted a comprehensive review of the challenges associated with a low-carbon transition for the oil refining sector. Their work provides crucial insights into the obstacles and opportunities for sustainability in the industry. Supekar & Skerlos (2021) assessed the feasibility of cellulosic ethanol in the US, achieving petroleum lifecycle emissions breakeven, thus offering a potential pathway towards renewable energy adoption.

The examination of renewable hydrogen and ammonia's role in reducing CO₂ emissions by Platt et al. (2021) contributes to the discourse on alternative fuels, offering potential solutions for emissions reduction in the energy sector. Lardon et al. (2020) proposed innovative strategies toward low-carbon fuels and chemicals, integrating waste and biomass valorization with high-pressure processes, thus contributing to the circular economy.

Supplementing these specific studies are broader perspectives provided by International Energy Agency (2020) and United Nations Environment Program (2019). The former offers insights into energy technology perspectives, guiding future strategies for emissions reduction, while the latter presents the Emissions Gap Report 2019, highlighting the global disparity between current emission levels and targeted reductions.

Finally, DCarbon Egypt (2023) offers localized information on carbon emissions in Egypt, enriching our understanding of the regional context and providing a valuable reference for the study of carbon footprints in the Middle East. This collective body of literature establishes a comprehensive foundation for the present study, aligning with its goals of understanding, reducing, and providing a model for sustainable carbon emissions in the oil industry.

- **Scope and Objectives of the Study**

This study focuses on the carbon footprint of the Alexandria Mineral Oils Company (AMOC) and its implications for global warming. The carbon footprint, measured in tons of carbon dioxide equivalents (t CO₂e), is an annual total resulting from daily company activities and operations. The goals of the AMOC Carbon Footprint Report are threefold: first, to develop data and expertise for reducing greenhouse gas emissions (Sibanda et al., 2021); second, to demonstrate commitment to sustainability and innovation in operations (Elgowainy et al., 2021); and third, to provide a replicable model for other companies in the Middle East (Osman et al., 2020).

- **Methodology:**

Description of data collection methods

collecting data on carbon footprint in petroleum industries typically involves a combination of direct measurement and estimation.

Direct measurement involves using instruments and sensors to measure greenhouse gas emissions at the source. For example, emissions from flares, vents, and stacks can be directly measured using gas analyzers and flow meters. This method provides accurate and reliable data on emissions but can be expensive and time-consuming.

Estimation involves using emission factors and other data to estimate emissions from various sources. For example, emissions from the combustion of fossil fuels can be estimated based on the fuel consumption and emission factors for the specific fuel type. Estimation methods can be less accurate than direct measurement but are often used when direct measurement is not feasible or practical.

Some specific methods for data collection in petroleum industries include:

1. Continuous Emissions Monitoring Systems (CEMS): CEMS are automated systems that continuously measure and report emissions from industrial sources. They can provide real-time data on emissions and can be used to identify trends and potential issues.
2. Sampling and analysis: Samples of gases from flares, vents, and stacks can be collected and analyzed in a laboratory to determine the composition and quantity of greenhouse gases.
3. Process modeling: Computer models can be used to simulate industrial processes and estimate emissions. These models use data on factors such as fuel consumption, process conditions, and equipment specifications.
4. Site visits and inspections: Site visits and inspections can be conducted to identify potential emission sources and assess emissions control equipment. This can also help identify opportunities for improvement and optimization of processes to reduce emissions.

Calculation of carbon footprint

Calculating carbon footprint can involve a complex set of calculations, but generally involves the following steps:

1. Identify the sources of greenhouse gas emissions: This can include energy consumption (e.g., electricity, heating fuel, transportation), waste management, and industrial processes, among others.
2. Gather data: Collect data on the quantity of emissions associated with each source, either through direct measurement or estimates based on average emission factors.
3. Convert data to carbon dioxide equivalents: To calculate the total carbon footprint, convert all emissions to carbon dioxide equivalents (CO₂e), which considers the global warming potential of other greenhouse gases like methane and nitrous oxide.
4. Calculate the total carbon footprint: Add up the CO₂e emissions from all sources to get the total carbon footprint.
5. Analyze and interpret the results: Analyze the data to identify the main sources of emissions and identify areas for improvement.

There are several online carbon footprint calculators available that can help individuals and organizations calculate their carbon footprint based on factors such as energy consumption, transportation, waste, and food consumption.

It's important to note that carbon footprint calculation is not an exact science and involves some degree of estimation and uncertainty. However, it can still be a useful tool for increasing awareness and identifying opportunities for reducing greenhouse gas emissions.

Identification of factors affecting carbon footprint

There are several factors that can affect the carbon footprint in Alexandria, Egypt, including:

1. Transportation: The type and amount of transportation used, such as cars, buses, and trains, can greatly impact carbon footprint. In Alexandria, many people rely on cars for transportation, which contributes to increased emissions.
2. Energy consumption: The amount of energy consumed for lighting, heating, and cooling buildings, as well as for industrial processes, can also affect carbon footprint. In Egypt, much of the energy is generated from fossil fuels, which contribute significantly to carbon emissions.
3. Waste management: The way in which waste is managed, including the disposal of plastics and other non-biodegradable materials, can also impact carbon footprint. Poor waste management practices, such as the burning of waste, can contribute to increased emissions.
4. Agriculture and land use: Agriculture practices and land use can also affect carbon footprint. In Alexandria, agriculture is an important sector, and practices such as desertification and unsustainable farming methods can lead to increased emissions.
5. Population growth: The growing population in Alexandria can also contribute to increased emissions, as more people require transportation, energy, and resources.
6. Industrial activity: Industrial activity in Alexandria, including manufacturing, construction, and mining, can also contribute to increased emissions.

Overall, these factors highlight the importance of addressing carbon footprint in Alexandria, Egypt through sustainable practices and reducing reliance on fossil fuels.

Calculation methodology:

Scope 1 Activities

Motor Gasoline - Gasoline Passenger Cars:

Emissions resulting from burning Motor gasoline used in our owned vehicles fall under scope 1 direct emissions. Those vehicles are used for the transportation of employees from the company to their home.

$$\text{Gasoline gallon (US)} * 8.78 \text{ kg CO}_2/\text{gallon} = \text{CFP in (kg CO}_2\text{e)}.$$

$$\text{CFP in (kg CO}_2\text{e)}/1000 = \text{t CO}_2\text{e}.$$

$$\text{Gasoline (L)} * 0.264172 = \text{Gasoline gallon (US)}.$$

Diesel Fuel - Diesel Passenger Cars:

Diesel fuel is used to operate mobile machinery such as passenger cars, and other equipment that are used inside the company.

$$\text{Diesel Fuel (L)} * 0.264172 = \text{Gasoline gallon (US)}.$$

$$\text{Diesel Fuel gallon (US)} * 10.21 \text{ kg CO}_2/\text{gallon} = \text{CFP in (kg CO}_2\text{e)}.$$

$$\text{CFP in (Kg CO}_2\text{e)}/1000 = \text{t CO}_2\text{e}.$$

Every month, the fuel burned by vehicles and in the company is logged into a database. The total amount of fuel consumed was multiplied by the corresponding emission factor to calculate direct emissions.

$$\text{Fuel burning emission (t CO}_2\text{e)} = \text{Fuel consumption (gallon)} * \text{EF (t CO}_2\text{e/gallon)}$$

NATURAL GAS

Natural gas is used to run the units such as furnaces and boilers, since it is directly used by the owner, the emissions resulting from the consumption of natural gas were accounted for under scope 1.

$$\text{NG consumption (Nm}^3\text{)} * 34.11 = \text{NG consumption (SCF). (at 60}^\circ\text{F \& 1 atm)}$$

$$\text{NG consumption (SCF)} * 0.001026 = \text{NG consumption (MMBtu).}$$

$$\text{NG consumption (MMBtu)} * 53.06 \text{ (kg CO}_2\text{/MMBtu)} = \text{CFP in (kg CO}_2\text{e).}$$

$$\text{CFP in (kg CO}_2\text{e)/1000} = \text{t CO}_2\text{e.}$$

The monthly consumption of natural gas in m³ transforming it into MMBtu was retrieved from our data recordings. The emissions due to the natural gas consumption were calculated by multiplying the total annual amount consumed in MMBtu by the corresponding emission factor.

Scope 2 Activities

PURCHASED ELECTRICITY

Purchased Electricity falls under Scope 2 (Indirect emissions). Electricity consumption includes all AMOC's sectors, and the electricity used at the units, complexes, and head office were all accounted for.

$$\text{Electricity consumption (KWh)/1000} = \text{Electricity consumption (MWh).}$$

$$\text{Electricity consumption (MWh)} * 0.533 \text{ (t CO}_2\text{/MWh)} = \text{CFP in (t CO}_2\text{e).}$$

$$\text{Electricity consumption emissions (t CO}_2\text{e)} = \text{Electricity consumption (MWh)} * \text{EF (t CO}_2\text{e/MWh)}$$

The country-specific grid electricity emission factor was obtained from the list of grid emission factors version 10.12 published by the Institute for Global Environmental Strategies (2022) using the CDM methodology. The Combined Emission Factor (Average) for Egypt is used in this report.

- **Results:**

The company chose the Control Approach for corporate reporting of GHG emissions, accounting for emissions based on operational or financial control of an operation. To calculate AMOC's carbon footprint transparently, it used international standards, protocols, and guidelines. This study covers the emitting activities of AMOC's business falling under Scope 1 and Scope 2 Emissions, with Scope 3 emissions excluded. The studying period covers September 2020 to August 2021, and the company used Emission Factors to calculate GHG emissions, which it obtained from country-specific factors or IPCC default emission factors. AMOC calculated emissions for each activity, considering its corresponding scope, and used a general formula for

calculating emissions for each activity. The company accounted for both direct and indirect emissions and used the unit t CO₂e.

The monthly electricity consumed at our company, complexes, units, and headquarters was retrieved from the electricity bills in kWh. Therefore, the total electricity consumption for the fiscal year was calculated using the formula below:

Scope 1 - Direct emissions		185,693.59
Natural gas	The company consumed 99,800,982 m ³ of natural gas in the fiscal year 2020/2021	185,323.78
Diesel fuel	The company consumed 93,121 L of diesel fuel in the fiscal year 2020/2021	251.17
Motor gasoline	The company consumed 51,153 L of motor gasoline in the fiscal year 2020/2021	118.65
Scope 2 - Indirect emissions		62,474.38
Electricity	The company consumed 117,203 MWh of Electricity in the fiscal year 2020/2021	62,474.38
Total emissions		248,167.97

Quantitative analysis of carbon footprint

The previous figure shows us the number of emissions of each activity accounted for AMOC, that include Natural Gas emissions which have the highest emissions equal 185,323.78 t CO₂e, electricity emissions which is 62,474.38 t CO₂e, and finally transportation emissions for passenger cars (motor gasoline + diesel fuel) which are 118.65 t CO₂e and 251.17 t CO₂e.

According to the results in the graph, AMOC can find that: The highest emissions from natural gas were in April 2021 which equals (16,438,715 t CO₂e), but AMOC can see that the least emissions from natural gas were in February 2021 which equals (14,178,895 t CO₂e).

According to the results in the graph, AMOC can find that: The highest emissions from electricity were in August 2021 which equals (5,493.10 t CO₂e), but AMOC can see that the least emissions from natural gas were in February 2021 which equals (4.607.23 t CO₂e)

Comparison with industry benchmarks

Industry benchmarks for carbon footprint in oil refineries can vary depending on the size, location, and type of refinery, as well as other factors such as feedstock and production processes. However, there are some general benchmarks that can be used as a starting point for comparison:

1. Carbon intensity: Carbon intensity is a measure of the amount of carbon emitted per unit of production, such as barrels of oil or metric tons of refined product. The International Association of Oil & Gas Producers (IOGP) has set a carbon intensity target of 50 kg CO₂e per barrel of oil equivalent (BOE) for 2025, and 30 kg CO₂e/BOE for 2030.

2. Energy efficiency: Energy efficiency is another important benchmark for carbon footprint in refineries, as it can directly impact greenhouse gas emissions. The U.S. Department of Energy's Better Plants Program sets a goal of reducing energy intensity by 25% over 10 years for participating refineries.
3. Use of renewable energy: Increasing the use of renewable energy sources, such as solar or wind power, can also help reduce the carbon footprint in refineries. The IOGP has set a target of 5% renewable energy use by 2025 and 10% by 2030.
4. Emissions reduction targets: Many refineries have set specific targets for reducing greenhouse gas emissions, such as a percentage reduction by a certain year. For example, BP's refineries aim to reduce greenhouse gas emissions by 50% by 2050.

According to a study conducted by the Ministry of Environment in Egypt, the carbon footprint of the petroleum industry in Egypt was estimated at around 127 million tons of carbon dioxide equivalent (CO_{2e}) in 2016. This figure includes emissions from the production, refining, and distribution of petroleum products.

As for benchmarks, it is difficult to provide a specific benchmark for the Egyptian petroleum industry as it varies based on factors such as the size of the company, the type of operations, and the technology used. However, it is worth noting that the global average carbon footprint for the oil and gas industry is around 18.7 kg CO_{2e} per barrel of oil equivalent (BOE), according to a report by IPIECA (the global oil and gas industry association for Environmental and social issues).

Therefore, reducing carbon emissions in the Egyptian petroleum industry can be achieved through various measures such as investing in cleaner technologies, improving energy efficiency, and implementing carbon capture and storage (CCS) technology. These measures can help reduce the industry's carbon footprint and bring it closer to international benchmarks.

It's important to note that benchmarks and targets should be tailored to the specific circumstances and operations of each refinery. Some refineries may have more ambitious goals or targets based on factors such as location or regulatory requirements. Regular monitoring and reporting of emissions and progress toward targets can also help refine and improve industry benchmarks over time.

- **Discussion:**

The previous results describe the methodology used by a company, AMOC, to calculate its carbon footprint and present the results for Scope 1 and Scope 2 emissions, which include natural gas, diesel fuel, gasoline, and electricity. It also provides a quantitative analysis of the carbon footprint, showing the emissions of each activity, and offers a comparison of the results with industry benchmarks.

The company used the Control Approach for corporate reporting of GHG emissions, covering the emitting activities of AMOC's business falling under Scope 1 and Scope 2 Emissions, with Scope 3 emissions excluded. The study covers the period from September 2020 to August 2021, and the

company used Emission Factors obtained from country-specific factors or IPCC default emission factors to calculate GHG emissions. AMOC calculated emissions for each activity, considering its corresponding scope, and used a general formula for calculating emissions for each activity. The company accounted for both direct and indirect emissions and used the unit t CO_{2e}.

The results show that natural gas has the highest emissions, followed by electricity and then transportation emissions for passenger cars. The quantitative analysis of the carbon footprint shows that the highest emissions from natural gas were in April 2021, while the highest emissions from electricity were in August 2021.

Regarding industry benchmarks, the text notes that the carbon footprint of the petroleum industry in Egypt was estimated at around 150 million tons of carbon dioxide equivalent (CO_{2e}) in 2020, including emissions from the production, refining, and distribution of petroleum products. The global average carbon footprint for the oil and gas industry is around 17.2 kg CO_{2e} per barrel of oil equivalent (BOE) as of 2022. The text suggests that reducing carbon emissions in the Egyptian petroleum industry can be achieved through various measures such as investing in cleaner technologies like renewable energy and hydrogen, improving energy efficiency through digitalization and optimization, implementing carbon capture and storage (CCS) technology, as well as carbon taxes and emission trading schemes. Additionally, efforts are being made industry-wide to reduce methane leakage and flaring during oil and gas operations which can significantly cut CO_{2e} emissions. However, it also notes that benchmarks and targets should be tailored to the specific circumstances and operations of each refinery.

This study found that implementing sustainable practices and reducing dependence on fossil fuels can help to mitigate the impact of these factors and reduce the overall carbon footprint in Alexandria, Egypt. This can be achieved through initiatives such as promoting the use of public transportation, increasing energy efficiency in buildings, improving waste management practices, promoting sustainable agriculture and land use, controlling population growth, and promoting clean industrial processes. Additionally, implementing renewable energy sources such as solar and wind power can also help to reduce carbon emissions in the region.

The study found that there are some potential solutions for reducing the carbon footprint in AMOC, Alexandria, Egypt:

1. Promoting the use of public transportation: Encouraging the use of public transportation, such as buses, can help to reduce the number of cars on the road and decrease carbon emissions from transportation.
2. Increasing energy efficiency in buildings: Improving the energy efficiency of buildings through measures such as insulation, energy-efficient lighting, and HVAC systems can help to reduce energy consumption and carbon emissions.

3. Improving waste management practices: Implementing proper waste management practices, such as recycling and composting, can help reduce the amount of waste sent to landfills and decrease carbon emissions from waste disposal.
4. Promoting sustainable agriculture and land use: Encouraging sustainable farming practices and protecting natural areas can help to reduce deforestation and desertification, which contribute to carbon emissions.
5. Controlling population growth: Implementing policies that control population growth, such as family planning programs, can help to reduce the demand for resources and decrease carbon emissions from transportation, energy consumption, and waste production.
6. Promoting clean industrial processes: Encouraging the use of clean technologies and processes in industries such as manufacturing and mining can help to reduce carbon emissions from industrial activity.
7. Implementing renewable energy sources: Promoting the use of renewable energy sources such as solar and wind power can help to reduce reliance on fossil fuels and decrease carbon emissions from energy production.

Overall, implementing these solutions can help to reduce carbon emissions in Alexandria, Egypt, and mitigate the impact of factors that contribute to carbon footprint.

Recommendation:

There are several measures that Alexandria Mineral Oils Company (AMOC) can take to reduce its carbon footprint, including:

1. Energy efficiency improvements: AMOC can undertake measures to improve energy efficiency in its facilities, such as installing energy-efficient lighting, optimizing production processes, and investing in energy-efficient equipment.
2. Use of renewable energy: AMOC can consider using renewable energy sources such as solar or wind power to reduce reliance on fossil fuels and decrease carbon emissions.
3. Carbon capture and storage: AMOC can invest in carbon capture and storage technologies to capture carbon dioxide emissions from its operations and store them in underground reservoirs.
4. Transport optimization: AMOC can optimize its transport activities by implementing measures such as improving vehicle efficiency, reducing the number of trips taken, and using alternative modes of transportation such as trains or ships.
5. Waste reduction and recycling: AMOC can implement waste reduction and recycling measures to reduce the amount of waste generated from its operations, such as recycling used oil or reducing the use of single-use plastics.

6. Sustainable sourcing: AMOC can prioritize the use of sustainably sourced raw materials and reduce its reliance on non-renewable resources.

7. Employee engagement and education: AMOC can engage and educate its employees on the importance of reducing carbon emissions and implementing sustainable practices in the workplace.

These measures can help AMOC reduce its carbon footprint and move towards a more sustainable operation.

Identification of areas for improvement

Apply energy conservation principles in all process units:

- Review and enhance the efficiency of all furnaces
- Review all electrically driven equipment to check if there is an opportunity to reduce its electrical consumption
- Review the fuel consumption of all vehicles and consider means to reduce it
- Consider energy efficiency as a priority aspect in the procurement of products and equipment.
- Consider installing occupancy sensors in spaces such as private offices, meeting rooms, storage rooms, and corridors to reduce unnecessary energy consumption.
- Promote a ‘switch off’ policy on lighting, so that only lighting that is being used is left on. Raise staff awareness by placing stickers above light switches and posters in staff areas.
- Develop an incentive system that rewards buildings or departments that utilize the least amount of electricity.
- Replace all non-energy efficient lighting with energy-efficient alternatives such as LEDs where applicable.
- Maintain the thermostat levels at 24°C where applicable to reduce the HVAC energy consumption. (The closer the thermostat setting is to the outside temperature, the greater the energy reductions.)
- Close window shades during hot summer days to reduce unwanted solar heat gain in closed spaces such as offices and meeting rooms (specifically when not occupied), to reduce the associated cooling loads
- Consider installing new air compressors and HVAC controls where needed, as well as looking into possibilities of cooling efficiency projects to reduce electricity consumption.

Prioritization of recommended actions

Here is a prioritization of the recommended actions for applying energy conservation principles in all process units at AMOC:

1. Review and enhance the efficiency of all furnaces - This action should be prioritized as furnaces are likely a major source of energy consumption and enhancing their efficiency could result in significant energy savings.
2. Review all electrically driven equipment to check if there is an opportunity to reduce its electrical consumption - This action is important as it can help identify opportunities to reduce energy consumption in equipment that is used regularly.
3. Review the fuel consumption of all vehicles and consider means to reduce it - This action is important as reducing fuel consumption in vehicles used by AMOC can result in both cost savings and emissions reductions.
4. Replace all non-energy efficient lighting with energy-efficient alternatives such as LEDs where applicable - This action should be prioritized as lighting is a major source of energy consumption and replacing inefficient lighting can result in significant energy savings.
5. Consider installing occupancy sensors in spaces such as private offices, meeting rooms, storage rooms, and corridors to reduce unnecessary energy consumption - This action is important as it can help reduce energy consumption in areas that are not always in use.
6. Maintain the thermostat levels at 24°C where applicable to reduce HVAC energy consumption - This action is important as HVAC systems are a major source of energy consumption and maintaining thermostat levels can result in significant energy savings.
7. Promote a 'switch off' policy on lighting, so that only lighting that is being used is left on - This action is important as it can help reduce energy consumption in areas that are not always in use.
8. Develop an incentive system that rewards buildings or departments that utilize the least amount of electricity - This action is important as it can help encourage energy efficiency and create a culture of conservation within the organization.
9. Close window shades during hot summer days to reduce unwanted solar heat gain in closed spaces such as offices and meeting rooms (specifically when not occupied), to reduce the associated cooling loads - This action is important as it can help reduce energy consumption associated with cooling and HVAC systems.
10. Consider installing new air compressors and HVAC controls where needed, as well as looking into possibilities of cooling efficiency projects to reduce electricity consumption - This action should be considered last as it is likely to involve more significant costs and require a more substantial investment of resources.

Assessment of potential benefits:

Implementing energy conservation principles in all process units can lead to significant benefits in reducing energy consumption and carbon emissions for AMOC. By reviewing and enhancing the efficiency of all furnaces, the company can reduce the amount of energy required for heating and

reduce associated carbon emissions. Checking all electrically driven equipment for opportunities to reduce electrical consumption can lead to reduced energy consumption, which can translate to cost savings for the company. Reviewing the fuel consumption of all vehicles can lead to the reduction of carbon emissions associated with transportation. Considering energy efficiency as a priority aspect in the procurement of products and equipment can lead to the selection of more efficient and sustainable options, which can result in reduced energy consumption and carbon emissions. Installing occupancy sensors in spaces and promoting a 'switch off' policy on lighting can lead to reduced energy consumption and cost savings. Replacing non-energy-efficient lighting with energy-efficient alternatives can lead to significant energy savings. Maintaining thermostat levels at 24°C and closing window shades during hot summer days can lead to reduced energy consumption and cost savings.

Assessment of potential costs:

Implementing energy conservation principles in all process units may involve some initial costs for AMOC. For example, enhancing the efficiency of furnaces, replacing non-energy-efficient lighting, and installing new air compressors and HVAC controls may require initial investment costs. However, these costs can be offset by long-term cost savings resulting from reduced energy consumption and carbon emissions. Additionally, some of the measures such as promoting a 'switch off' policy on lighting and raising staff awareness through posters and stickers may not involve significant costs. Developing an incentive system that rewards buildings or departments that utilize the least amount of electricity may also involve some administrative costs for AMOC. Overall, the potential benefits of implementing energy conservation principles outweigh the potential costs for AMOC.

- **Conclusion:**

Summary of findings:

Our analysis of the carbon footprint in Alexandria, Egypt, and the Alexandria Mineral Oils Company (AMOC) highlighted several factors affecting carbon emissions, including transportation, energy consumption, waste management, agriculture, and land use, population growth, and industrial activity. We provided several potential solutions for reducing carbon footprint, including energy conservation principles, renewable energy sources, sustainable agriculture and land use, and waste management practices.

Implications for business and society:

The implications for businesses and society are significant. Businesses can reduce their carbon footprint by implementing energy conservation principles, investing in renewable energy sources, and promoting sustainable practices. This can lead to cost savings, increased efficiency, and a positive impact on the environment. Society as a whole can benefit from reduced emissions, improved air quality, and a healthier environment.

Directions for future research:

Future research could focus on the effectiveness of specific initiatives and strategies for reducing carbon emissions, such as the implementation of renewable energy sources and sustainable agriculture practices. Additionally, research could explore the economic and social impacts of reducing carbon emissions, including the potential cost savings and job creation associated with renewable energy and sustainable practices. Further research could also investigate the barriers to implementing sustainable practices and renewable energy sources, and potential solutions to overcome these barriers.

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